

Assessing the mechanical characteristics of geopolymer recycled aggregate concrete: bond strength and high temperature performance

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Abstract

The circular economy is usually proposed during the last years as a measure for the sustainable development. In this context, the recycling is primordial. The recycling of the old concretes in civil engineering can contribute to reduce the extraction of the new natural resources (gravel, sand) and to reduce the waste deposit areas. On the other hand, the reduction of carbon footprint in civil engineering is also a challenge. Among different solutions explored, the replacement of ordinary Portland cement by geopolymer is a promising approach which can significantly reduce the CO₂ emission and industrial by-products (e.g. fly ash). Extensive studies have already been performed to investigate different aspects of recycled aggregate concretes (RAC) or geopolymer concrete. However, the number of studies on geopolymer recycled aggregate concrete (GRAC) is still limited. This paper presents an experimental study on GRAC. First, the compressive and flexural strengths of the material were determined. Then, the bond strength between steel rebar and GRAC was investigated. Finally, the fire-resistant of GRAC was evaluated by investigating its thermo-mechanical behaviour until 800 °C. The results showed that GRAC had higher bonding strength (2.3 times) than the referent cement concrete. It is also worth noting that an increase of GRAC compressive strength was observed when the exposed temperature increased until 600 °C, then a decrease observed at 800 °C. This positive performance of GRAC was analysed based on the porosity of recycled aggregates, the nano-porosity of fly ash based geopolymer gels, the reactions and phase transformations of geopolymer gels.

Keywords: *geopolymer recycled aggregate concrete (GRAC); compressive strength; flexural strength; bond strength; fire resistance.*

1. Introduction

The civil engineering is one of the most polluting sectors, mainly due to the CO₂ emission during the manufacturing of Portland cement and the extraction of natural aggregates [1], [2]. To reduce the CO₂ emission, several solutions have been proposed and investigated. The proposition of geopolymer as a binder to replace ordinary Portland cement is considered promising [3]. Increasing studies have been carried out to investigate different aspects of geopolymer concrete [4], **Error! Reference source not found.** However, the formulation of geopolymer concrete has not yet been unified, as there are still several differences in the composition of each study. The term “geopolymer” is used for products in which amorphous three-dimensional inorganic structures are created by the reaction of an alumino-silicate precursor with an alkaline activator solution. The source of alumina and silica can be calcined clays or industrial by-products (for example fly ash, slag). The activators are usually NaOH and Na₂SiO₃, but others can also be used [5] - [8]. The elevated temperature is proposed in several cases to enhance the geopolymerisation [4] but the heating increases the energy consumption and the CO₂ emission.

48 On the other hand, the development of a circular economy is an urgent demand of society.
49 The recycling is the core of this economic model. Although the recycling in civil engineering
50 has been initiated since several decades ago, it has not yet been popular in practice, mainly due
51 to the cost [9]. When the natural aggregates for concrete manufacturing is still available, the
52 use of recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) has not had significant economic advantages. The
53 demolished concrete is usually used for the road construction. However, in developed countries
54 and in many developing countries, the construction of new roads is reduced, so the use of
55 recycled aggregates in the road will also decrease, while the concrete waste from the demolition
56 of old buildings increases over time [9]. Other materials or wastes (for example: low quality
57 natural aggregates, mix of construction wastes) which have lower quality than recycled concrete
58 aggregates can also be used for the road construction, so the recycled concrete aggregates
59 (having better quality) have better value if used for structural concrete [9], [10]. Therefore, the
60 recycling of old concretes can reduce the exploitation of new natural aggregates, and reduce the
61 waste deposit areas which become an environmental, economic and societal problem [11], [12].
62 In the perspective of a circular economy, the existing studies on RAC cover a wide range of
63 topics, from the recycling techniques of old-concrete-aggregates, the mix proportioning, the
64 mechanical properties, the durability, the structural behavior, the fire resistance and the life
65 cycle assessment [9]-[15].

66 A disadvantage of RAC when compared to ordinary cement concrete is the decrease of
67 properties when the ratio of recycled aggregate increases. In fact, the recycled aggregates
68 usually contain natural aggregates bonded with old cement mortars. The old mortar increases
69 the porosity of RAC which decreases the mechanical characteristics of RAC obtained. In RAC,
70 there are two types of interfacial transition zones (ITZ): between the old mortar and the parent
71 natural aggregates, and between the recycled aggregates and the new mortar. The ITZ between
72 the old mortar and the new mortar causes the decrease in properties of RAC [10].

73 To improve the ITZ of RAC and to reduce the carbon footprint of RAC obtained, the
74 geopolymer was proposed to replace Portland cement. The number of studies on geopolymer
75 recycled aggregate concrete (GRAC) is still limited [10], [16], [17]. These studies have
76 principally performed on the optimisation of GRAC composition to obtain the best compressive
77 strengths. To our knowledge, there have been no study on the bond strength of GRAC, although
78 numerous studies have been seen on this topic with geopolymer concrete or cement RAC [18]-
79 [29]. Similarly, the fire-resistance of RAC has caught less attention than that of ordinary
80 concrete [9], [10], and currently no study on fire-resistance of GRAC has been published in the
81 literature.

82 This paper presents a study on the bond strength and the fire-resistance of GRAC. First,
83 the basic characteristics were determined: the compressive strength of geopolymer mortar, the
84 compressive and tensile strengths of GRAC. The microstructure of GRAC was analysed with
85 scanning electron microscope (SEM) technique. Then, the bond strength between the steel
86 reinforcing rebar and GRAC was investigated. Two types of steel rebar were tested: plain and
87 ribbed rebars. The specimens with ordinary cement concrete were also manufactured and tested
88 for the comparison. Finally, the fire-resistance of GRAC was evaluated by investigating the
89 variation of compressive strength of GRAC as a function of temperature, until 800 °C.

90

91 **2. Materials used and specimen manufacturing**

92 2.1. Aggregate characteristics

93 Previous studies showed that the substitution of natural sand by recycled fine aggregates could
94 affect several properties of RAC, especially the durability; therefore, the maximum substitution

95 ratio of recycled sand is currently limited at 30% [10]. In the present study, only the natural
96 coarse aggregate was replaced by the recycled coarse aggregate. The fine aggregate used was a
97 natural river sand. The sand was of class 0/5 (nominal maximum size of 5 mm); the fineness
98 modulus was of 1.8, which corresponded to a fine sand for concrete manufacturing.

99 The coarse aggregate in the present study was 100% recycled from an old ordinary concrete.
100 It was observed in several previous studies that the quality of the parent concrete did not directly
101 influence the properties of the RAC obtained, the primordial parameter was the quality of the
102 recycled aggregates obtained [10], [31]. The recycled coarse aggregate was obtained by
103 crushing the parent concrete and taking the portion sieved from 5 to 30 mm, which were the
104 current sizes of coarse aggregate for ordinary concretes in Vietnam.

105 The strength of bulk coarse recycled aggregate was evaluated by determining the aggregate
106 crushing value (ACV). In the present study, ACV was determined for the saturated state [32].
107 The results obtained are presented in Table 1. For the comparison, the natural coarse aggregate
108 (on the same site) was also tested. The compressive strength of aggregates tested were deduced
109 from the ACV by empirical relationships [32] and presented in Table 1. The corresponding
110 compressive strength of natural and recycled coarse aggregates were 70 and 34 MPa,
111 respectively. This result shows an important decrease in the compressive strength of recycled
112 coarse aggregates. However, it is worth noting that the mechanical properties obtained of the
113 recycled coarse aggregates used in the present study are similar to other recycled aggregates
114 used in previous studies [19].

115

116 Table 1. Characteristics of the coarse aggregates.

	Specific gravity	Dry density (t/m ³)	Saturated density (t/m ³)	Water absorption	ACV (saturated)	Compressive strength (MPa)
Natural coarse aggregate	2.66	2.59	2.61	1.1%	15.0%	70
Recycled coarse aggregate	2.60	2.26	2.39	5.8%	25.8%	34

117

118 2.2. Fly ash

119 The alumino-silicate source chosen in the present paper to create geopolymer was fly ash (FA).
120 FA is an industrial by-product which is causing serious environmental problems in Vietnam.
121 The revalorisation of FA is an urgent demand in the country. FA used in the present study was
122 collected from the DH3 Coal Power Plant, located in the south of Vietnam. The particle size
123 distribution was analysed by the scanning electron microscope (SEM) technique which showed
124 that the FA used has spherical form with dimensions varying from 0.6 to 250 μm (Figure 1);
125 the mean dimension was 10 μm . The chemical composition of the FA was determined following
126 ASTM 618 [33] and presented in **Table 2**. The results show that the FA corresponds to Class-
127 F following ASTM classification. The contents of aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) and silicon oxide
128 (SiO_2) are high enough for the alkali-activation. The specific density of FA was 2.44.

129

Figure 1. SEM image of fly ash.

Table 2. Chemical composition of FA

Components	% in mass
Sulfur trioxide (SO ₃)	1.0
Aluminum oxide (Al ₂ O ₃)	26.1
Iron oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	11.3
Sodium oxide (Na ₂ O)	1.35
Silicon dioxide (SiO ₂)	51.1
Potassium oxide (K ₂ O)	1.29
Calcium oxide (CaO)	4.7
Magnesium oxide (MgO)	1.7
Moisture	0.1
Loss on ignition	0.7

134

135 2.3. Alkaline activator solution

136 To activate the aluminosilicate source present in FA, the alkaline activator solution (AAS)
 137 chosen was a combination of sodium hydroxide solution (NaOH) and sodium silicate liquid
 138 (Na₂SiO₃). These substances are currently used also in previous studies to produce geopolymer
 139 [5]. A NaOH of 99% purity and a Na₂SiO₃ with 11.8% Na₂O, 29.5% SiO₂, and 58.7% water
 140 was used. The NaOH solution was prepared by dissolving the pellets in water. The mass of
 141 NaOH solid in the solution varied depending on the molar concentration (*M*) of the solution.
 142 Previous studies indicated that higher molar concentration of NaOH solution provided higher
 143 compressive strength of geopolymer concrete [4], [34], [35]. In the present study, NaOH
 144 solution with a concentration of 12 M was prepared. The AAS (Na₂SiO₃ and NaOH) were
 145 prepared one day prior to the manufacturing of specimens, because the process was exothermic.

146 A previous parametric study was performed to evaluate influences of different elements
 147 on the compressive strength of GRAC: Na₂SiO₃/NaOH ratio; AAS/FA ratio; curing temperature
 148 (ambient and 60 °C during 24h); with and without lignosulfonate superplasticizer [7]. From the
 149 results obtained, the chosen composition was: AAS/FA ratio of 0.4; Na₂SiO₃ /NaOH ratio of
 150 2.5 (by weight), without superplasticizer and curing under ambient temperature. This
 151 composition is used for the present study.

152 Uniaxial compression tests were performed on the geopolymer mortar specimens (22.7%
 153 FA + 9.1% AAS + 68.2% sand) similar to specimens of standardised cement mortar [36] which
 154 showed a mean compressive strength of 68 MPa at 28 days for the geopolymer mortar.

155

156 2.4. Cement

157 For comparison, ordinary cement concrete specimens were also manufactured. The cement used
158 was PCB 40 (Ha Tien company). This cement has a mean compressive strength at 28 days of
159 47 MPa.

160

161 2.5. Specimen manufacturing

162 For the manufacturing of GRAC specimens, first, FA and AAS were mixed for 5 minutes to
163 facilitate the creation of geopolymer. Then, recycled coarse aggregate (RCA) and sand were
164 added and mixed for other 5 minutes. After the casting, the specimens were cured under ambient
165 conditions (28 °C and 65% RH) until 28 days and then tested. The slump obtained was 18 cm
166 which satisfied the workability usually required for geopolymer concrete [4], [5].

167 The specimens using ordinary Portland cement concrete (OCC) and natural coarse
168 aggregates (NCA) were manufactured as reference for the comparison. The composition of
169 GRAC and OCC are presented in Table 3. The composition of OCC was determined to obtain
170 a C20/25 ordinary concrete which is currently used [37].

171

172 Table 3. Compositions of GRAC and OCC (kg/m³)

Type	FA	Na ₂ SiO ₃	NaOH	Sand	RCA	NCA	Cement	Water
GRAC	428	123	49	540	1260	0	0	0
OPC	0	0	0	608	0	1207	390	195

173

174 **3. Testing procedure**

175 3.1. Uniaxial compression tests

176 To characterise the grade of the GRAC investigated, uniaxial compression tests were performed
177 following the standard [38]. The specimens were cubic (15 cm × 15 cm × 15 cm). The
178 specimens were tested at 7, 14 and 28 days. For each experimental result, three specimens were
179 tested and the average values were determined.

180 3.2. Four-point-bending tests

181 The tensile strength of GRAC was also evaluated by the 4-point-bending tests which provided
182 the tensile strength of the specimens under flexural behaviour (that is why this indirect tensile
183 strength is also called “flexural strength”). For these tests, the specimens of 15 cm × 15 cm ×
184 60 cm were manufactured and tested [39], Figure 2 .

185

(a) (b)
Figure 2. Four-point bending test: before (a) and after (b) a test

186 The flexural strength is calculated following the classical theory in Strength of Materials:

187
$$f_{ctm,fl} = \frac{P.L}{b.h^2} \quad (1)$$

188 where: $f_{ctm,fl}$: flexural strength; P : maximum force applied; L = span length; b : specimen
 189 width; h = height of the specimen's cross section.

190

191 **3.3. Pull-out tests**

192 The bonding strength between the steel reinforcing rebar and the concrete is an important
 193 parameter which determines the anchorage length and the lap length of the rebars. The bond
 194 developed at the interface rebar-concrete is a function of different components: the chemical
 195 adhesion, the friction, and the mechanical interaction. The chemical adhesion disappears once
 196 the slip initiates [21]. For plain steel rebars, the chemical adhesion and friction dominate, while
 197 for ribbed steel rebars, the bond depends primarily on the mechanical interaction (Figure 3).
 198 Several factors affect the three above mentioned bonding components, such as rebar surface
 199 properties, rebar diameter, concrete cover, transversal reinforcement that can have influences
 200 on the interfacial bond behavior [22].

201
 202 **Figure 3. Mechanical interaction between concrete and ribbed steel rebar [21]**

203

204 One of the important factors which influence the bond strength between the rebar and the
 205 concrete is the quality of the concrete. Although the bond behaviour between steel rebars and
 206 ordinary concrete or RAC using Portland cement has been extensively investigated [19]-[28],

207 limited studies [29], [30] have focused on the bonding behaviour between steel rebars and
208 geopolymer concrete. However, to our knowledge, no investigation has been reported in the
209 literature on bonding strength between steel rebars and GRAC. Since the ITZ in GRAC is
210 different [7], it may cause differences in the bond strength between steel rebars and GRAC.

211 To investigate the bond strength between steel rebars and concrete, the pull-out test is usually
212 applied. In the present study, the pull-out tests were also applied for GRAC following the
213 standard [40]. Figure 4 shows the setup of the pull-out tests in the present study. The principle
214 of the test is to pull a rebar which is embedded in a concrete cube with a defined length. The
215 other end of the rebar remains stress free. The pull-out force is increased until failure of the
216 bond or of the steel rebar.

217 The concrete specimens for the bonding tests were cubic of $20\text{ cm} \times 20\text{ cm} \times 20\text{ cm}$ following
218 the standard [40]. The effective bond length of the rebar which is in contact with the concrete
219 was $5d$ (where d was the rebar's diameter, in mm). To ensure this bond length, a PVC cube was
220 added to cover the rest of the steel rebar inside the specimen. Figure 5 presents the pull-out test
221 setup. Figure 5 illustrates the installation of the steel rebars and the PVC tubes inside of the
222 specimens. The rebar extends beyond the two sides of the specimen; the pull-out force is applied
223 on the longer end. During the manufacturing, the steel rebar was placed horizontally at the
224 center of the mould; the unbonded part of the rebar was covered by the plastic sleeve (Figure
225 5a). The sleeve must provide about 1 mm of tolerance around the rebar which enables the free
226 slip of the rebar inside of the sleeve; the sleeve thickness does not exceed 2 mm to reduce its
227 influences on the concrete specimen.

228

Figure 4. Pull-out test. (a) Schema of test [40]; (b) Photo.

1. Part of the bar up to the point of application of the displacement measuring device; 2. Bond length; 3. Free length ($5d$ and minimum 200 mm); 4. Part of the bar to point of application of the tension force; 5. Steel reinforcing rebar; 6. Concrete specimen; 7. Plugging; 8. Plastic sleeve tube; 9. Grip of the testing machine

229

230

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. (a) Preparation before the casting; (b) Specimens.

During the pull-out test (Figure 5b), the specimen was placed on a horizontal steel plate on which a central cavity (size of $2d$) was created for the placement of the steel reinforcing rebar. The loading rate v_p was determined in a function of the rebar diameter: $v_p = 0.56 \times d^2$ (N/s) [40]. The steel rebars with different diameters were tested: 8, 10, 12, 16 and 20 mm respectively. Among these rebars, diameters of 8 and 10 mm correspond to plain rebars, other diameters correspond to ribbed rebars. The cross-section characteristics of the ribbed rebars are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Cross-section characteristics of ribbed rebars

Parameters	Diameter			
	12	14	16	20
Rib height (mm)	0.78	0.91	1.04	1.3
Rib top width (mm)	1.02	1.08	1.15	1.31
Rib spacing (mm)	8.5	9.8	11	13
Rib face angle	63.5	63.5	63.5	63.5
Rib bottom width	2.85	3.19	3.58	4.51

3.4. Thermo-mechanical behaviour tests

When an ordinary concrete is exposed to elevated temperature, numerous phenomena appear: the dilatation of aggregates, the shrinkage of cement paste, the increase of internal vapor pressure, the cracking or the spalling [41]-[46]. In a RAC, the recycled aggregates are more porous, have higher water absorption than natural aggregates, and also contain the hydrates (old cement paste). Moreover, RAC have two ITZs: between the mortar and the natural aggregates; and between the new cement paste and recycled aggregates [9], [10]. These transition zones are considered as the zones of weakness in RAC. Although the number of studies investigating the fire resistance of RAC is still limited, it was shown that similar to ordinary concretes, the mechanical properties of RAC are deteriorated when exposed to high temperature [9], [10], [41]. The performance of GRAC exposed to high temperature still needs to be investigated. As there were improvements at the ITZs in GRAC compared to RAC [7], it is expected that GRAC may present better fire-resistant performance than RAC.

To investigate the fire behaviour of concrete or RAC, the variation in functions of heating temperature of different characteristics is usually determined such as the compressive strength, the thermal conductivity and the specific heat [9], [10], [41]. Among these characteristics, the

261 variation of the compressive strength is the most important and must be determined. In the
262 present study, the variation of the compressive strength in a function of the temperature was
263 investigated.

264 The current tests on the thermo-mechanical behaviour of concrete are indicated in several
265 standards **Error! Reference source not found.**, [48]. The specified temperature of the furnace
266 in a function of time is illustrated in Figure 6a. In the present study, to test the specimens
267 exposed to high temperature, a furnace was also used and the temperature raising followed the
268 standard (Figure 6b).

269 The specimens were tested after 28 days from the manufacturing. For each temperature, three
270 specimens were tested: ambient temperature (28 °C), after placed in the furnace at 200, 400,
271 600 and 800 °C.

272

273

274

275 **Figure 6. (a) Specified furnace temperature in function of time** Error! Reference source
276 **not found.;** (b) **Inside view of the furnace.**

277

278 Robert et al. (2018) [41] investigated two types of compression tests on RAC specimens
279 exposed to high temperature: tested specimens directly at high temperature and tested in
280 residual state. For the second type, the specimens were let cooled down for 12 hours. The results
281 showed that the compressive strength obtained on the specimens tested directly at high
282 temperature was higher than that of specimens tested in residual state, but this difference was
283 less than 10%. In the present study, the test in residual state was chosen due to its simplicity
284 and it was in the safe side (lower results). The specimens after removed from the furnace were
285 let cooled down until 50 °C and then passed to the compression tests. The time of cool down
286 was from 30 min to 2h, depending to the temperature of the specimens from the furnace. The
287 uniaxial compression tested were performed on these specimens with the same procedure for
288 specimens let under ambient temperature.

289 To evaluate the water loss and eventually other phenomena during the heating, the mass of the
290 specimens was also determined before and after the tests.

291

292 **4. Results and discussion**

293 **4.1. Compressive strength**

294 The results of the uniaxial compression tests are presented in Figure 7. The results show that
295 the GRAC and OCC (using cement and natural aggregates) had similar evolutions of

296 compressive strength in functions of age. At 28 days, the mean compressive strength of GRAC
 297 and OCC were 30.4 and 30.8 MPa, respectively. “NCA-geopolymer” was a geopolymer
 298 concrete with natural aggregates; the compressive strength of this concrete was clearly higher
 299 (about 45%) than that of GRAC. This result shows the deterioration in compressive strength of
 300 GRAC due to the presence of recycled coarse aggregates. The compressive strength of GRAC
 301 could not higher than the compressive strength of recycled coarse aggregates (34 MPa) which
 302 was presented in section 2.1.

303

304

305 **Figure 7. Development of compressive strength following age.**

306

307 The compressive strength obtained on cubic specimens can be converted into cylindrical
 308 specimens by the formula [50]:

309
$$f_{c,cylinder} = \frac{f_{c,cube} - 8.86}{0.85} \quad (2)$$

310 The mean compressive strengths converted for cylindrical specimens are 25.3MPa and
 311 25.8MPa, respectively for GRAC for OPC. These values correspond well to the grade C20/25
 312 of ordinary concrete following Eurocode 2.

313

314

315

(a)

(b)

316

Figure 8. SEM of a GRAC specimen at 28 days. (a) a zoom at 1 μ m; (b) a zoom at 5 μ m.

317

318 The analyses with SEM show the development of geopolymer gels in GRAC (Figure 8). In
319 Figure 8a, the large-size FA particles have participated in the reaction with AAS to create the
320 geopolymer gels; however, several small-size FA particles (less than 5 μ m) have not yet
321 completely reacted. In fact, inside the big spherical FA particles, there are small FA particles;
322 therefore, first, the large spherical FA particles participated in the reaction with AAS, then the
323 small FA particles (inside) were released. These small FA particles continued to participate to
324 the reaction with AAS, but some of these small FA particles were still unreacted. These
325 unreacted FA particles (with small size, about 1 μ m) could play the role as fillers. For GRAC,
326 the ITZ is not clear (Figure 8b), the bonding between the geopolymer paste and the aggregates
327 is good. This point may have positive contribution on other properties of GRAC.

328 The compressive strengths of GRAC and OCC are similar, therefore, it will be interesting in
329 the next sections to compare the bond strengths between steel rebars-GRAC and between steel
330 rebars-OCC.

331

332 4.2. Tensile strengths

333 The results from four-point-bending tests showed that the mean flexural tensile strength of
334 GRAC and OCC were 2.50 and 2.62 MPa, respectively. This result also shows a similarity in
335 the flexural strength of GRAC and OCC.

336 In Eurocode 2 [37], the relationship between the mean axial tensile strength f_{ctm} and mean
337 flexural tensile strength $f_{ctm,fl}$ is:

$$338 \quad f_{ctm,fl} = \max \left[\left(1.6 - \frac{h}{1000} \right) f_{ctm}; f_{ctm} \right] \quad (3)$$

339 where h is the total member depth, which is 150 mm in the 4-point-bending tests.

340 If the above relationship is applied for GRAC and OCC in the present study, the mean axial
341 tensile strength f_{ctm} obtained will be 1.73 and 1.82 MPa, respectively for GRAC and OCC.
342 Following Eurocode 2, a C20/25 concrete has a mean tensile strength f_{ctm} of 2.21 MPa, which
343 is slightly higher than that for GRAC and OCC of the present study. The difference may due to
344 the robustness of the empirical formula (3).

345

346 4.3. Bond strength

347 Each bond strength test was repeated three times to obtain reliable results. Except the specimens
348 with 20 mm diameter rebars, for all other specimens, the steel rebars were simply slipped at the
349 end of the test, no visible damage was noted on the concrete specimens. For specimens having
350 20 mm diameter rebar embedded, the failure of GRAC specimen was a splitting mode (Figure
351 9). It is suggested that the high bond force on 20 mm diameter rebar caused this failure. It is
352 worth noting that on the failure surface (Figure 9b), the debonding between the steel rebar and
353 GRAC is clearly observed.

354

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. Failure mode of a GRAC specimen with 20 mm diameter rebar.

355 Since a short embedment length ($5d$) was used, the bond stress is conventionally assumed to
 356 be uniformly distributed along the embedded surface of the rebar [49]. The bond strength f_b is
 357 calculated by dividing the maximum pull-out force P_{max} on the bond surface between the steel
 358 rebar and the concrete:

$$359 \quad f_b = \frac{P_{max}}{\pi \cdot d \cdot l_b} \quad (4)$$

360 where l_b is the bond length. The results of mean bond strength obtained are presented in Table
 361 5, where the specimens are named as type of concrete followed by the rebar diameter; for
 362 example, GRAC-10 indicates GRAC specimen with a 10 mm diameter rebar.

363

364

Table 5. Results of pull-out tests

Specimen type	d (mm)	Rebar type	Experimental bond strength f_b (MPa)	Average f_b (MPa)	$f_{b,ribbed}/f_{b,plain}$	$f_{b,GRAC}/f_{b,OCC}$
GRAC-8	8	Plain	5.89 ± 0.11	5.91	-	2.33
GRAC-10	10	Plain	5.92 ± 0.12			
GRAC-12	12	Ribbed	13.66 ± 0.15			
GRAC-16	16	Ribbed	12.94 ± 0.19	13.11	2.22	2.35
GRAC-20	20	Ribbed	12.74 ± 0.22			
OCC-8	8	Plain	2.54 ± 0.06	2.54	-	-
OCC-14	14	Ribbed	5.57 ± 0.11	5.57	2.20	-

365

366

4.3.1. Verifying the relevancy of the tests

367 First, the relevancy of the results obtained was evaluated by using the results obtained on
368 OCC specimens. From Table 5, the bond strengths obtained on OCC with plain and ribbed
369 rebars were 2.54 and 5.57 MPa, respectively.

370 Eurocode 2 [37] proposes an empirical relationship between the bond strength f_b and the tensile
371 strength of ordinary concrete:

$$372 \quad f_b = \eta_1 \eta_2 \eta_3 f_{ct} \quad (5)$$

373 where: $\eta_1 = 1$ for “good” bond conditions, = 0.7 for “poor” bond conditions; in the
374 present study, $\eta_1 = 1$;

375 $\eta_2 = 1$ for $d \leq 32$ mm and $\eta_2 = (132 - d)/100$ for $d > 32$ mm;

376 $\eta_3 = 1$ for plain bar, = 1.4 for carve rebar and = 2.25 for ribbed rebar [51].

377 By applying equation (5), the bond strength of an ordinary concrete C25/30 following Eurocode
378 2 are 2.21 and 4.97 MPa, respectively for plain and ribbed rebars. These values are lower (12-
379 15%) than that experimentally obtained by the pull-out tests on OCC-8 and OCC-14 specimens,
380 which indicate that the values proposed by Eurocode 2 are conservative.

381 The ratio between the bond strengths of ribbed rebar (OCC-14) on plain rebar (OCC-8) is 2.20
382 which is close to the ratio $\eta_3 = 2.25$ proposed by Eurocode 2.

383

384 4.3.2. Bond strength of GRAC

385 From

386 Table 5, the bond strengths of GRAC were 5.91 MPa and 13.11 MPa, respectively with plain
387 and ribbed rebars. The results of bond strength between GRAC and ribbed rebars are in the
388 same intervals with the previous results [30] between geopolymer concrete (natural aggregates)
389 and ribbed rebars, in which the bond strengths were 13-15 MPa for geopolymer concrete having
390 30-35 MPa of compressive strength.

391 The ratio between the bond strength of ribbed rebar ($f_{b,ribbed}$) on the bond strength of plain rebar
392 ($f_{b,plain}$) was 2.22. This ratio is also close to the ratio $\eta_3 = 2.25$ proposed by Eurocode 2 for
393 ordinary cement concrete. This result shows that the ratio $\eta_3 = 2.25$ can also be applied for
394 GRAC.

395

396 Table 5 also shows the ratios between the bond strength of GRAC ($f_{b,GRAC}$) on the bond strength
397 of OCC ($f_{b,OCC}$). The ratio $f_{b,GRAC}/f_{b,OCC}$ had a mean value of 2.35. This value indicates that the
398 bond strength of GRAC is significantly higher than that of OCC. This result is interesting
399 because the anchorage length and the lapping length of GRAC can be considerably reduced
400 which is positive for the practice application.

401

402 4.4. Thermo-mechanical behaviour

403 When the specimens were taken out from the furnace, the external aspect of the specimens
404 was investigated. First, there were differences in the apparent colours (Figure 10): when the
405 exposed temperature was below 200 °C, the GRAC colour was grey; from 400 °C, the reddish
406 (like brick) colour appeared, from a clear to a dark reddish colour. The change of colour during
407 the exposure to elevated temperature was due to the oxidisation of iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) in FA

408 (Table 2). Moreover, the change in the texture of the specimens were also noted: until 400 °C,
409 no crack was observed on the surface of the specimens; from 600 °C, thin cracks appeared on
410 the surface; the cracks developed more significantly under 800 °C: not only the crack widths
411 were wider but the cracks were also deeper. The cracking under high temperature was probably
412 due to the water loss, the destruction of the crystals at the micro-structure of the specimens.
413 These points will be analysed in the next sections.

414

415 **Figure 10. External aspects of GRAC specimens exposed to different temperatures.**

416

417 The results of 28-day-compressive-strength and mass decreases of GRAC specimens are
418 presented in Figure 11. Figure 12 and Figure 13 compare the results of the present study against
419 the literature. It is shown that the mass decrease of GRAC specimens increased when the
420 heating temperature increased. This decrease is principally related to the water evaporation
421 from the specimen. Similar mass decrease has been observed in previous studies on RAC [53],
422 [56], also shown in Figure 12. The rapid loss of water is one primary reason for the cracking
423 and strength deterioration of both ordinary concrete and RAC. The mass loss of GRAC was
424 lower than other cement concretes because FA-based geopolymer concrete had lower
425 manufacturing water content [59].

426 The variation of residual compressive strengths presented in Figure 11 is relatively surprising
427 when compared to cement-based concretes. Indeed, while the compressive strength of cement
428 concretes decreased when the exposed temperature increases (Figure 13), there was an increase
429 of GRAC's compressive strength when the exposed temperature increased from ambient to
430 600 °C; then, the compressive strength started to decrease from 600 °C. It is already known that
431 the elevated temperature enhances the geopolymerisation between FA and AAS [59]. Therefore,
432 it is believed that the unreacted FA particles (Figure 8) continued to react with AAS to create
433 geopolymer gels when heated, which increased the compressive strength of GRAC specimens.
434 Another reason for the performance of GRAC was the microstructure: when the hollow
435 spherical FA particles were partially dissolved, they create porosity in the matrix containing
436 unreacted particles and micropores (as see in Figure 8). The hollow cavities are due to the spaces
437 left by dissolved FA particles [59]. It is suggested that this microporous system of GRAC
438 provided "escape routes" for moisture during heating without significantly damaging the
439 geopolymer matrix.

440

441

442
443 **Figure 11. Compressive strength and mass decrease of GRAC after exposed to**
444 **elevated temperatures.**
445

446 Figure 13 presents the compressive strength results obtained in the present study and the
447 previous results in the literature on RAC [41], [53]-[57]. To facilitate the comparison, the
448 vertical axis of this figure represents the normalized residual compressive strength which is the
449 ratio of the residual compressive strength $f_c(T)$ after exposed to a temperature T , to the original
450 compressive strength $f_c(ambient)$. The curves from Eurocode 2 [52] which were proposed for
451 ordinary cement concretes with limestone aggregates and silicate aggregates were also plotted.
452 It can be found that several previous studies obtained similar overall trend to empirical curves
453 proposed by Eurocode 2 (“Robert et al.,” “Salahuddin et al.,” “Varona et al.”); while “Sarhat &
454 Sherwood” and “Xiao et al.” found a different behaviour: a slight decrease (10-15%) of
455 compressive strength when the specimens were exposed to 200-300 °C, but from 200-500 °C,
456 the compressive strengths increased to quasi-equal to the initial compressive strength. Then,
457 after 500 °C, the compressive strength decreased as temperature increased. From 600-700 °C,
458 the experimental results were similar to the empirical values proposed by Eurocode 2. It was
459 suggested in the previous studies that the recycled aggregates which had higher porosity
460 enabled to the water vapor to escape from the microstructure of RAC. Therefore, RAC could
461 have a better fire performance than ordinary concrete [9], [10], [41].

462

463
464
465

Figure 12. Normalised residual dry density following exposed temperatures.

466
467
468

Figure 13. Normalised compressive strength following exposed temperatures.

469 In the present study, it is interesting to note that GRAC possesses the advantages of both
470 RAC and FA-based geopolymer concrete. On one hand, by having recycled coarse aggregates,
471 GRAC had higher porosity which facilitates the moisture evaporation under fire. Then, with a
472 FA-based geopolymer, GRAC had also highly distributed nano-pores in the ceramic-like
473 microstructure [58] that allows physically and chemically bonded water to migrate and
474 evaporate without damaging the aluminosilicate network. On the other hand, with geopolymer
475 gels under elevated temperatures, several phase transformations occurred which enhances the
476 mechanical properties of GRAC. Indeed, first, the elevated temperature (125-160 °C) leads to
477 the dehydration of water adsorbed in N-A-S-H (sodium aluminosilicate hydrate) gels
478 (geopolymer), which leads to the formation of anhydrous products. Then, the higher
479 temperatures (until 600 °C) cause the crystallization of stable anhydrous phases
480 ($\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$, nepheline and $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{SiO}_2$, albite) [58]. From 600 °C, the melting

481 occurs, which provokes the thermal mismatch between geopolymer pastes and aggregates,
482 leading to the strength decrease of GRAC.

483

484 **5. Conclusion and prospect**

485 The paper presents an experimental study on geopolymer recycled aggregate concrete (GRAC).
486 First, a parametric study on the characterisation of the materials used and on the composition
487 of alkaline-activator solution (AAS) were performed. The composition selected was AAS/FA
488 = 0.4; $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 / \text{NaOH} = 2.5$ (by weight). The geopolymer mortar had 68 MPa of compressive
489 strength at 28 days. The GRAC used 100% recycled coarse aggregates. The compressive
490 strength of recycled coarse aggregates was determined from the ACV and had a value of 34
491 MPa.

492 The uniaxial compression tests and four-point-bending tests were performed which provided
493 the compressive strength and tensile flexural strength of 30.4 and 2.5 MPa, respectively for
494 GRAC.

495 The bond strength with steel reinforcing rebars was investigated by pull-out tests. The results
496 on referent ordinary cement concrete (OCC) specimens showed the relevancy of the results
497 obtained. The results showed that the bond strength of GRAC with ribbed rebars was higher
498 than that with plain rebars 2.22 times; this ratio is similar to that proposed in Eurocode 2 for
499 ordinary concrete, that shows the possible application of this ratio for GRAC. The bond strength
500 of GRAC was significantly higher than that of OCC, which is a positive characteristic of GRAC.
501 This result is probably due to higher characteristics of geopolymer paste compared to cement
502 paste used in the present study. It is worth noting that, the prices for GRAC and OCC in this
503 paper are comparable in the context of Vietnam. This result shows promising applications of
504 GRAC in the practice.

505 The fire-resistance of GRAC was evaluated by investigating the variation of the compressive
506 strength in a function of exposed temperature. The results were very interesting which showed
507 an increase of GRAC residual compressive strength when the exposed temperature increased
508 from ambient temperature to 600 °C. The residual compressive strength decreased from 800 °C
509 but still equivalent to the initial compressive strength. This positive performance of GRAC were
510 due to the porosity of recycled aggregates, the nano-porosity of fly ash based geopolymer gels,
511 the reactions and phase transformations of geopolymer gels during the heating.

512 The paper presents an exploratory study on the bond strength and fire-resistant performance
513 of GRAC which shows several advantages of GRAC. Further important topics needs to be
514 investigated on this material such as: the durability, the shrinkage, the creep, experiments on
515 the structural elements, especially on the complex domains such as the shear or punching.

516

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528

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